

AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: ON THE WAY TO A MARKET ECONOMY

Akbar Yusupovich Qurbonov

Lecturer of the Department of digital economy of the Institute of
entrepreneurship and pedagogy Denov, Uzbekistan

Abstract: The Republic of Uzbekistan lives in conditions of full political sovereignty. However, political independence and the sovereignty we have won may remain empty words without an adequate independent economic basis. The basic concepts and principles of creating an independent economic basis are now clearly outlined in Uzbekistan. They were formulated and brought to the whole people by the First President I. A. Karimov.

Keywords: digital economy, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, agro-industrial complex

Introduction

The Republic of Uzbekistan lives in conditions of full political sovereignty. However, political independence and the sovereignty we have won may remain empty words without an adequate independent economic basis. The basic concepts and principles of creating an independent economic basis are now clearly outlined in Uzbekistan. They were formulated and brought to the whole people by the First President I. A. Karimov. These concepts and principles are fully based on the maximum consideration of the historical past, on the traditions and customs of the people and the modern realities of the socio-economic and political situation of the country. The main thing in them is what is supposed about their own path of renewal and progress, and the most important distinguishing feature is the social orientation to improve the lives of workers. The main thing now is purposeful accelerated progress along the path of their practical implementation. And here there are issues of fundamental importance and determining our strategy and

tactics in the process of creating this economic basis. Among the many industrial and economic complexes of the agro-industrial complex, a special role is assigned. It is the largest both in terms of the use of resource potential and in terms of the importance of the formation of national income, the food fund and the fund of non-food consumer goods. [2] The agro-industrial complex as an important structural subdivision of the economy in the form of an embryo has been formed for a long time. We believe that in the conditions of transition to market relations, the place and importance of the sphere of implementation is changing so significantly that it is impossible not to single it out as an independent block in the structure of the agro-industrial complex. In market conditions of management, due to the absence of a state monopoly on sales, the end consumer himself or through the corresponding diverse wholesale structures dictates his conditions to the manufacturer, and the latter is obliged to take into account their specific demand. In other words, the ultimate goal of producers and the agro-industrial complex as a whole can be achieved only if its product is sold, i.e. the reproduction process is completed after the product has completely passed all its stages. Therefore, it is not surprising that in developed capitalist countries, agro-industrial production is focused primarily on the market, which is not only an integral element of the agro-industrial complex system, but also the final and controlling function of agro-industrial production and acts as an agribusiness system in which production and the market are merged into a single whole, and competition acts primarily as a struggle for the market, for the buyer and consumer. [2]

In this regard, two conclusions are of particular relevance: firstly, that the formation and development of marketing services in the structure of the agro-industrial complex for optimal finding answers to the questions: what, how, when

and how much to produce, when and how to sell goods, are a necessary condition for the transition to market economic relations; secondly, that the formation of an extensive and multi-layered network of procurement and implementation structures is one of the important factors of the normal functioning of the agro-industrial complex in new conditions. With the acquisition of political sovereignty by the Republic and the transition to market relations, the agro-industrial complex faced new more complex tasks, different scales of production, there was an objective need to accelerate the reduction of the huge gap between the achieved and prospective level of development of the agro-industrial complex, gradually achieving first relative, and then, for some types, complete food and agro-raw independence. [1]

To achieve the goals in these new conditions, the power of the agro-industrial complex, its productive abilities must meet and correspond to the following five qualitative characteristics: to what extent the system of economic relations in the agro-industrial complex provides economic freedom to individuals and legal entities and takes into account the role of man as the main agent of production; to what extent the state of the agro-industrial complex as a whole and its various structural components reflects the level of modern development of the scientific and technical process and meets the requirements of progressive technical, technological and organizational foundations of agricultural production; to what extent optimal quantitative and qualitative proportions are fully observed between all blocks and links of the agro-industrial complex at the level of horizontal and vertical links in order to ensure the synchronicity of its work; what is the provision of the agro-industrial complex with initial production resources, the degree of their involvement in the production and economic turnover and the level of its use; how

are the requirements of compliance with the ecological balance and respect for natural resources and the environment taken into account. [2]

The transition to a market economy objectively presupposes the formation and development of all its basic foundations, which include: diverse forms of ownership and, above all, private ownership of the means of production; freedom of entrepreneurship and choice of all subjects of this property; personal interest as the main driving motive of the behavior of each economic unit; free or perfect competition; free market pricing for goods and services. Independent Uzbekistan's own path of socio-economic development is determined by a number of circumstances, including the real situation, which has developed as a heavy legacy of the totalitarian system with its inefficient economic mechanism and in which it is necessary to update all aspects of the economy, the national and historical past, the peculiarities of the way of life and mentality of the Uzbek people. Therefore, the problems of maximum consideration of these features and non-standard approaches to ensure an accelerated and relatively painless transition to market relations are of exceptional importance. Among them, of particular importance are: demographic dynamics and high population density per unit of cultivated land, as well as the scarce and limiting water factor with the prevailing low rates of their use, objectively put forward the problem of a qualitative breakthrough in the productive power of each hectare of land, each cubic meter of water as the most urgent task.; when forming a new sectoral structure of the national economy, it is necessary to take into account the fact that in the agro-industrial complex, production with an unfinished cycle prevails, which was formed at the stage of primary processing of raw materials and the manufacture of semi-finished products.

In this regard, it is necessary to accelerate the process of structural restructuring of the economy, where new industries and new types of production should be created. Consequently, the role and importance of deep consideration of the law of absolute and comparative advantages, strengthening of integration and cooperative ties within the state economic space is dramatically increasing. [1] The conclusion here is unambiguous: the level and structure of the Republic's economy should have a basis that will not only ensure the successful solution of burning socio-economic problems, but also allow for an independent political dialogue with everyone, without looking around.

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